

can be conducted in early generations of breeding programs. QTL mapping of rice yield and related characters is the first step to apply marker technology to breeding programs for improving yield potential.

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Use of DNA markers in constructing multilines

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Construction of multilines, each with a major resistance gene(s) for different Korean blast races, is under way to characterize resistance genes and to test whether deployment of multiple resistance genes in this fashion will provide durable resistance to blast disease. Resistance genes were introgressed from different donors into the commercial cultivars. Identifying molecular markers linked to these genes is essential to speed up the process of making the multilines.

Three isolines (BC₅F₃) constructed using Daeseongbyeo as a donor and Chucheongbyeo as the recurrent parent were used in the gene-tagging experiment. Each line shows resistance to blast isolates KJ-201, KJ-301, and KI-313, respectively (see table). These three isolates were used individually for inoculation during near-isogenic line (NIL) development. Genetic analysis of Daeseongbyeo indicated that

Autoradiograph showing hybridization pattern of RG213 in Daeseongbyeo (D), pooled three isolines (I), and Chucheongbyeo (R) DNA digested with the following enzymes: *Bam*HI (1), *Eco*RI (2), *Eco*RV (3) *Scal* (4), and *Hind*III (5). The isoline resistant to race KJ-201 only showed the same restriction pattern as the donor with *Scal*.

Reaction^a of differential varieties and parents to four races of rice blast fungus.

Variety	Race			
	KJ-101	KJ-201	KJ-301	KI-313
<i>Differential variety</i>				
Tetep	R	R	R	R
Tongil	R	R	R	S
Nongbaeg	S	S	R	R
Jinheung	S	S	S	S
<i>Parents</i>				
Daeseongbyeo	S	R	R	R
Chucheongbyeo	S	S	S	S

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.

one dominant gene conditions resistance to isolates KJ-201 and KI-313 and two dominant genes condition resistance to KJ-301 (Kim 1994).

Fifteen RFLP markers previously reported to be linked to major blast resistance genes in different rice germplasm (McCouch et al 1993) and six microsatellite markers mapped to nearby regions were surveyed for polymorphism among the lines. One restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) marker, RG213, on chromosome 6 showed polymorphism between the isogenic lines (see figure).

Using the segregating populations, this marker is being tested to determine whether it is linked to the resistance gene (KJ-201).

We also have used random amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) technique to identify primers that amplify DNA that is polymorphic between the NILs. Three hundred RAPD primers were used to analyze the genome. Each primer amplified 3.1 loci on average (corresponding to about 930 loci). This survey revealed one locus putatively linked to resistance and demonstrated that the lines were nearly isogenic to their recurrent parent, Chucheongbyeo. This marker also is being tested.

Other sets of NILs were developed using two recurrent parents and four donor parents. Based on their reaction to races and phenotype, six NILs were selected and subjected to yield trials and hot-spot leaf blast nursery test. The reaction degree of six NILs appeared to be less severe than that of their respective recurrent parent.

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Breeding methods

Development of cold-tolerant rice through anther culture

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Rice grown in the high-altitude areas of the northeastern hills of India is exposed to cold at flowering and ripening stages. It often suffers from incomplete panicle exertion, asynchronous flowering, and poor seed set, resulting in yield losses of 20-50%. In addition, due to a long crop season, only one crop of rice can be grown in these areas. Conventional breeding thus requires more time.

Doubled haploid (DH) lines are increasingly being used to make breeding programs practical (Foroughi-Wehr and Wenzel 1990). We developed cold-tolerant lines by compressing the breeding cycle through anther culture.

To incorporate cold tolerance into a high-yielding genetic background, IR70 was crossed with Khonorullo, a local red-kernel variety with cold tolerance at the reproductive phase. F_1 -derived anther culture yielded 21 DH lines of which nine were selected. We tested these in the field for yield and yield-contributing characters. All nine yielded significantly more than did the better parent. Four lines—DH1, DH7, DH10, and DH21—retained 97.5, 72.8, 87.6, and 87.5% of the yield of the F_1 , respectively. Two lines exhibited desirable white kernels, and one, DH21, had a high number of spikelets panicle⁻¹ and good 1,000-grain weight. Among the light red kernel lines, DH1 was the most promising (Table 1).

Table 1. Comparison of doubled haploid (DH) lines with F_1 hybrids and parents. Barapani, India. 950 m above sea level.^a

	Days to maturity	Plant height (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers (no.)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield plant ⁻¹ (g)	Grain color (p3-W) ^b
P_1 (IR70)	145	57	5.0	123	8.1	16.8	0.4 ^c	W
F_1 (IR70/Khonorullo)	136	85	7.0	147	62.2	23.5	8.1	p2
P_2 (Khonorullo)	129	129	4.0	145	60.7	24.3	5.2	p3
DH1	133	87	3.8	203	77.3	22.0	7.9	p1
DH7	139	81	3.2	132	91.4	30.8	5.9	p1
DH10	130	78	3.2	77	94.8	30.0	6.2	W
DH21	140	101	4.1	159	81.5	25.0	7.1	W
CD at 5%		6.82	1.01	19.4	2.25	1.9	0.51	

^aAv yield of 5 plants. ^bW = white, p3 = red, p2 = light red, p1 = very light red. ^cLow yield due to cold prevailing throughout the life cycle of the plant.

Table 2. Performance of DH lines in the field at Barapani, India.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Panicle-bearing tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets panicle ⁻¹ (no.)	Spikelet fertility (%)	1,000-grain weight (g)	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)
IR70	89.4	10.4	24.4	105.8	72.6	23.0	3.1
Khonorullo	109.8	4.4	18.0	64.8	76.2	29.3	2.2
DH1	118.2	16.0	22.0	104.8	66.0	15.0	3.3
DH7	113.6	15.6	26.4	172.3	63.1	22.2	4.0
DH10	89.0	5.4	20.8	54.4	81.6	26.7	1.2
DH21	78.2	10.0	21.4	147.6	74.1	22.3	3.3

In field tests during 1994-95 kharif (at 950 m above sea level), DH7 yielded the most (4.0 t ha⁻¹), followed by DH21 and DH1, both at 3.3 t ha⁻¹. The better parent, IR70, yielded 3.1 t ha⁻¹ (Table 2).

Yield and vigor of the DH lines are either better than those of both parents or as good as those of the better parent, possibly because of in vitro screening of recombinants. Anther culture hastened the fixation of vigor not only by fixing homozygosity but by discriminating against less fit recombinants. Increasing the sound grains panicle⁻¹ of DH21 contributed to the higher yield over the better parent. We will conduct replicated yield trials during the next crop season.

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A comparison of the efficiency of four breeding methods

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Conventional breeding methods are successful in that they have been used to produce virtually all cultivars of small grain cereals, including rice. Their success rate per pedigree initiated is, nevertheless, low. Successful breeders must make hundreds of crosses to ensure that some promising lines emerge from each cohort of crosses.

We compared the efficiency of three breeding methods with that of single seed descent (SSD) in each of two crosses, Bg850/IR50 and 88-5328/ob255. The performance of F_6 lines extracted from each of these crosses by the pedigree (P), modified pedigree (MP), bulk (BL), and SSD methods were assessed for 13 quantitative characters in two completely